

The Role of Psychophysical Stress and Physical Activity in the Modulation of Psoriasis Symptoms – An Interdisciplinary Review

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Abstract

Psoriasis vulgaris is a chronic inflammatory skin disease influenced by psychophysical stress and lifestyle. Dysregulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis in psoriasis leads to impaired cortisol response and increased proinflammatory cytokine activity. Patients are also less physically active due to cutaneous symptoms and psychological barriers. This review aims to explore the impact of stress and physical activity on psoriasis progression. Chronic stress promotes neuroimmune dysregulation and flare-ups in psoriasis. Regular physical activity improves HPA axis function, reduces skin symptoms, and enhances mental well-being and quality of life. Physical activity represents a valuable adjunct in psoriasis therapy, not only by modulating inflammatory responses but also by mitigating the effects of chronic stress, a key factor in disease exacerbation. An integrated approach combining dermatological, neuroendocrine, and psychological perspectives may enhance treatment outcomes and patient quality of life. Despite the benefits, many patients avoid exercise, underscoring the need for personalized interventions. A literature review was conducted using PubMed and Google Scholar databases, covering studies from 2010 to 2025. Keywords included: “psoriasis,” “chronic stress,” “HPA axis,” “physical activity,” “cortisol,” and “cytokines.”

Keywords— Psoriasis, Chronic stress, HPA axis, Physical activity, Cytokines

1. INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis vulgaris is a chronic, relapsing inflammatory skin disease with an immunological basis, affecting approximately 2–4% of the general population worldwide. In genetically predisposed individuals, various components of the epidermis and dermis responsible for maintaining skin barrier integrity become dysregulated in response to environmental triggers or autoantigens. This persistent dysregulation of the skin immune system leads to a chronic inflammatory state characteristic of many chronic dermatological conditions [1]. Clinically, psoriasis presents with erythematous, scaling plaques most frequently located on the elbows, knees, scalp, and sacral region. Beyond the physical manifestations, the disease has a profound impact on patients' psychosocial wellbeing, leading to reduced quality of life and increasing the incidence of depression, anxiety disorders, and chronic psychological stress [2,3]. These psychosocial factors often interplay with the clinical course of the disease, influencing both severity and frequency of flare-ups.

In recent years, increasing attention has been devoted to the role of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and neuroimmunological stress mechanisms in the pathogenesis and course of psoriasis. Dysregulation of the HPA axis, including diminished cortisol response to stressors, may exacerbate

inflammation and affect dendritic cell and Th17 lymphocyte activity—key players in psoriatic lesion development [3,4].

Simultaneously, studies have shown that patients with psoriasis are less physically active than the general population, often due to pruritus, skin pain, psychological discomfort, and embarrassment [5]. However, physical activity has well-documented anti-inflammatory effects, reduces cortisol levels, normalizes HPA axis function, improves mental health, and may contribute to alleviating psoriasis symptoms [6,7].

The aim of this review is to present the current knowledge regarding the impact of chronic stress and physical activity on the course of psoriasis in adults. This interdisciplinary work integrates dermatological, neuroendocrinological, psychological, and physiological aspects, proposing practical implications for adjunct non-pharmacological treatment.

2. PSORIASIS—EPIDEMIOLOGY, PATHOPHYSIOLOGY, AND RISK FACTORS

Psoriasis is a common chronic inflammatory disease affecting approximately 125 million people worldwide [8,9]. It can manifest at any age, with typical onset between 18–39 years or 50–69 years [10]. Its etiology is multifactorial, involving genetic predisposition, environmental triggers, immune dysregulation, and lifestyle factors. Major risk factors include positive family history, infections, skin injuries, chronic stress, tobacco smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, obesity, and certain medications. Psoriasis is characterized by epidermal hyperproliferation and immune cell infiltration of the skin. Its pathogenesis involves complex interactions among keratinocytes, immune cells, and skin-resident cells. Dendritic cells, T lymphocytes (mainly Th1 and Th17), and pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-17, IL-22, and IL-23 play critical roles [11,12,13]. These mediators drive keratinocyte hyperproliferation, angiogenesis, and inflammatory infiltration in the dermis. In patients with psoriasis, elevated levels of IL-17 are observed not only in lesional skin and peripheral blood but also in uninvolved, non-lesional skin. Studies indicate that the primary sources of IL-17A in psoriatic skin lesions include neutrophils, Th17 cells, mast cells, CD8+ T cells, $\alpha\beta$ T cells, $\gamma\delta$ T cells, and innate lymphoid cells [14]. Neuroendocrine disturbances, including HPA axis dysregulation, are also observed in psoriasis patients, potentially intensifying inflammation in response to stress. Genetic factors account for up to 70–80% of disease susceptibility. The strongest genetic association is with the HLA-Cw6 allele (PSORS1), especially in type I psoriasis [15]. Other significant genetic variants include mutations in CARD14, involved in NF- κ B pathway activation [16]. Epidemiologically significant risk factors include active and passive tobacco smoking; the Nurses' Health Study demonstrated an increased risk in female smokers versus never smokers [17]. Air pollution has also been implicated; a 2024 study found that chronic exposure to PM2.5 and PM10 increased psoriasis risk, particularly in individuals with a family history [18]. Exposure to certain medications such as beta-blockers, lithium, antimalarials (hydroxychloroquine), interferons, imiquimod, and terbinafine can induce or exacerbate psoriasis [19].

3. ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS AND THE HPA AXIS IN PSORIASIS

Psychological stress, defined as tension and pressure perceived internally leading to anxiety or negative emotions, is a well-established trigger of psoriasis [20]. The HPA axis is the primary neuroendocrine regulator of stress responses. Activation leads to corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) release from the hypothalamus, stimulating adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) secretion by the pituitary, which in turn

induces glucocorticoid production via melanocortin 2 receptor (MC2-R) interaction, resulting in cortisol release. In healthy individuals, cortisol exerts potent anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokine expression (IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6) and leukocyte migration. Psoriasis patients, however, show impaired HPA axis responsiveness, contributing to chronic skin inflammation [20,21]. Physiologically, stress-induced activation of the local (cutaneous) HPA axis increases CRH expression in the skin, stimulating keratinocytes to produce inflammatory cytokines like IL-6 and IL-11. CRH also enhances adhesion molecule expression on keratinocytes—ICAM-1, HCAM, HLA-DR, and MHC class II molecules. Importantly, CRH activates the nuclear factor NF- κ B complex, a key transcription factor regulating genes involved in immune responses to oxidative stress, UV radiation, infections, and inflammatory stimuli, thereby sustaining chronic inflammation. Consequently, CRH-driven NF- κ B activation induces a pro-inflammatory keratinocyte phenotype that may initiate and perpetuate psoriatic lesions in patients exposed to chronic stress [12,20].

Stress testing using the Trier Social Stress Test (TSST) demonstrated that psoriasis patients have significantly blunted cortisol responses compared to healthy controls despite similar psychological stress levels, along with increased pro-inflammatory cytokine production post-stress exposure [4]. Richards et al. confirmed that patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis exhibit attenuated cortisol increases after psychosocial stress, indicative of partial HPA axis maladaptation [22]. Similar findings by Evers et al. showed reduced baseline and flattened diurnal salivary cortisol rhythms in psoriasis [23]. The CALIPSO Study (Hjorth et al.) found evening cortisol levels inversely correlated with disease severity (PASI) [24]. HPA axis dysfunction was more pronounced in patients with comorbid depression and anxiety, highlighting the psychodermatological complexity [25]. Kozłowska et al. observed increased ACTH and IL-17 levels alongside decreased cortisol in psoriasis, suggesting central and peripheral HPA axis dysregulation correlated with stress, PASI, and cytokine profiles [26]. Psychological stress also activates the autonomic nervous system, notably the sympathetic branch, releasing catecholamines (adrenaline, noradrenaline) and neuropeptides such as substance P. Substance P promotes skin mast cell degranulation, vascular permeability, and cytokine production, contributing to erythema and pruritus. Increased substance P-positive nerve endings are found in psoriatic skin, potentially explaining stress-induced symptom exacerbation. Catecholamines have dual effects—acute stress may be anti-inflammatory, but chronic elevation can impair epidermal barrier function and amplify immune responses [27,28,29]. Emotional stress is a commonly reported trigger of psoriasis onset and flares, with significant life events linked to disease relapse. Chronic stress fosters depression and anxiety, which may further disrupt HPA axis function, creating a vicious cycle of stress–hormonal imbalance–skin symptom worsening. Higher perceived stress levels (e.g., via PSS) correlate with increased PASI scores [30].

4. PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AS A REGULATOR OF STRESS AND IMMUNITY

Physical activity exerts multifaceted effects on neuroendocrine and immune systems. A key mechanism involves modulation of the HPA axis and inflammatory cytokine profiles, relevant to chronic inflammatory diseases like psoriasis. Regular moderate exercise induces adaptive HPA axis stimulation, yielding a more stable diurnal cortisol secretion pattern and improved stress response regulation. A meta-analysis by Zschucke et al. demonstrated that physically active individuals have steeper declines in daily cortisol rhythms, reflecting more efficient negative feedback and HPA axis control [31]. Additionally, regular exercisers show attenuated cortisol responses to psychosocial stressors. In a randomized trial by Zschucke et al., participants engaging in 30 minutes of running exhibited significantly reduced cortisol increases after the Maastricht Imaging Stress Task (MIST) compared to inactive controls [32]. Interleukin 6 (IL-6) plays a pivotal role, with concentrations rising up to several dozen fold during moderate-to-high intensity exercise.

Docherty et al. reviewed IL-6's anti-inflammatory properties: it induces IL-10 and IL-1 receptor antagonist (IL-1ra) production while inhibiting TNF- α synthesis. IL-6 acts endocrinologically, initiating an immunomodulatory cascade, and locally supports glucose metabolism and muscle regeneration [33,34]. In autoimmune patients, exercise training normalizes Th1/Th2 lymphocyte responses, shifting immunity towards a less pro-inflammatory phenotype. Teodoro et al. (2025) showed that regular exercise reduced TNF- α and IL-6 levels, decreased CD4/CD8 ratio, and increased IL-10 after 24 weeks, supporting Th1/Th2 balance. Acute exercise transiently elevated IL-4, IL-6, and IL-10, normalizing within an hour, indicating short-term immunomodulation [35]. Furthermore, physical activity regulates monocyte and macrophage function, lowering resting inflammatory markers CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6. Exercise decreases pro-inflammatory CD14⁺CD16⁺ monocytes and TLR expression on these cells, limiting cytokine production [36]. Similar immunoregulatory effects occur in individuals with HPA axis dysfunction and chronic stress; exercise improves cytokine balance, reduces cortisol response to stressors, and induces adaptive decreases in HPA axis reactivity. Zschucke et al. confirmed that regular exercise can lead to sustained hormonal response attenuation to psychosocial stress, indicative of neuroendocrine HPA axis adaptation [32].

5. PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN PSORIASIS PATIENTS – CHALLENGES AND THERAPEUTIC BENEFITS

Despite extensive evidence supporting physical activity's beneficial effects on immune and neuroendocrine function, psoriasis patients engage in regular exercise significantly less often than healthy individuals. Limiting factors include cutaneous symptoms (pain, itch, burning), psychological barriers (embarrassment, social anxiety, reduced self-esteem), and misconceptions that exercise exacerbates symptoms via sweating and mechanical irritation of affected skin areas.

A study by Young et al. (2020) involving 225 adults with psoriasis, divided into age groups 18–65 and >65 years, found that 52.8% of younger and 66% of older patients failed to meet minimum recommended physical activity guidelines. Negative correlations were found between PASI severity and time spent on physical activity ($r = -0.19$; $p = 0.04$), and between DLQI quality of life scores and activity levels ($r = -0.11$; $p = 0.04$), underscoring the influence of psychophysical barriers. Reported barriers included symptom exacerbation in mechanically stressed areas (elbows, knees), pain and itch during movement, social embarrassment during public exercise, and fears of symptom worsening [37]. Conversely, moderate, regular physical activity has been shown to reduce disease severity and improve patient quality of life. Sheppard et al. (2024) demonstrated that a 10-week aerobic and functional exercise program resulted in PASI-50 achievement, decreased depressive symptoms, and improved cardiovascular fitness and dermatological quality of life assessed by DLQI in both younger and older patients [6]. Considering multifactorial barriers limiting physical activity in psoriasis, personalized exercise prescriptions accounting for age, physical capacity, disease severity, and psychological comfort are essential. Low-impact exercises such as Nordic walking, yoga, aquatic therapy, and breathing exercises are well-tolerated and safe options for this population. Psoriasis significantly impairs patients' quality of life due to its chronic nature, burdensome cutaneous symptoms, and associated psychosocial comorbidities. One of the widely used instruments to assess quality of life in dermatology is the Dermatology Life Quality Index (DLQI). Studies indicate that physical activity programs can substantially improve DLQI scores in patients with psoriasis, translating into better daily functioning and reduced stress levels [6]. Physical activity exerts beneficial effects not only on cutaneous manifestations but also on the psychological aspects related to the disease. Regular exercise is

associated with decreased severity of pruritus and skin pain, reduction of chronic stress levels, and improvement in self-esteem and mood, which may contribute to the mitigation of depressive symptoms [38].

The literature describes various forms of physical activity and relaxation techniques that may support psoriasis therapy. Practices such as yoga and tai chi, through the integration of physical movement and mindfulness, contribute to improved physical fitness, stress reduction, and emotional stabilization [39,40]. Aerobic exercise exhibits anti-inflammatory properties, leading to a reduction in skin symptoms and enhancement of cardiovascular function [41]. Furthermore, mindfulness techniques combined with physical activity aid in more effective stress and disease management by increasing body and emotional awareness [42]. An interdisciplinary approach combining regular physical activity and relaxation techniques constitutes a valuable adjunct to psoriasis treatment, positively impacting patients' quality of life in both physical and psychological domains.

6. CONCLUSION

Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory disorder with complex etiology involving genetic, immunological, and environmental factors, including chronic stress. HPA axis dysregulation and neuroimmunological disturbances significantly contribute to disease development and exacerbations. Chronic stress exacerbates inflammation by disrupting cytokine balance and immunoregulatory mechanisms in the skin. Physical activity plays a multidimensional role in modulating immune and neuroendocrine systems. Regular moderate exercise stabilizes HPA axis function, lowers cortisol levels, and promotes anti-inflammatory cytokine production, potentially alleviating psoriasis symptoms. Concurrently, exercise benefits mental health and quality of life. Despite these advantages, many patients avoid physical activity due to symptoms, psychological discomfort, and fears of worsening skin lesions. Therefore, individualized exercise programs considering skin condition, physical ability, and psychological needs are vital. In summary, integrating dermatological, neuroendocrine, and psychological insights highlights physical activity as a valuable non-pharmacological adjunct in psoriasis management by reducing chronic stress and modulating inflammatory responses. Further research is needed to optimize exercise recommendations and maximize therapeutic benefits for this patient group.

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